

Community development through good governance – the case of Siem Reap Province, Cambodia

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Agenda

1. Introduction
2. Theoretical Background
3. Cambodia
4. Regional Economic Development Cambodia
 - Case: Community market Chong Kal District
 - Case: Tourism promotion and improvement in Khnar Po, Soutr Nikum
 - Case: O'Runteas Banh Fishery Community
5. Learning & Recommendations

Introduction

- Cambodian economy is undergoing a transformation from a strong focus on agriculture to a growing importance of the industry and services sectors
- Over the last 15 years stable growth rate of 7%
- Positively influenced the rural economy
- Poor households: agriculture still forms the backbone of the rural economy
- Better transport linkages and modern communication technology have improved linkages between rural and urban areas
- New economic opportunities for the local economy (e.g. access to markets, business services, agro-processing, tourism)
- Until now Cambodia's rural areas lacks behind
- Urban and rural areas are still characterized by significant socio-economic disparities

Introduction

- RGC: Strategic Framework for Decentralization and Deconcentration Reforms
 - reducing such disparities by fostering local economic development
- Subnational administrations (SNA) and councils are mandated to promote the local economy
 - insufficient capacities of local authorities
 - insufficient involvement of citizens
- Shortcomings: result in a precarious economic and employment situation of rural households in northwestern part
- Without substantial support, the SNAs will not be able to fulfill the mandate

Case study helps to observe the governance and investigates:

- *How can economic development in rural areas be enhanced?*
- *What support and governance is required to improve the situation in rural areas in Siem Reap Province- what are success factors and challenges?*

Background & Theoretical Concepts

- Deregulation of the public sector US, UK NIRL 1980 foundation of the governance concept
- No consensus on the definition of "governance"
- Broadly understood, governance is defined as all activities with the goal of implementing a certain order in social structures, involving many different actors
- Good governance: implies changes in political organization, the representation of interests, processes for public debate and policy decision making
- Areas: hierarchies (state governance), markets, networks, and societies
- Interfaces between the state, private actors and society are of particular interest
- Research on tourism and governance has increased
- Network Approach successful

Success Factors and Challenges

Success factor

- Participation of the various stakeholders
- Network establishment
- Participatory development
- Knowledge sharing and trust amongst the stakeholders
- Exchange of information, use of synergies and coordination of action

Challenges

- No established consensus
- Lack of proper assigning the roles and responsibility
- Different levels of commitment, trust and availability of resources among parties
- Stakeholder selection process
- Regional challenges

Cambodia

Cambodia

- Prior to the latest changes, the government of Cambodia recognized the importance of decentralisation and established political frameworks accordingly
- Government designed a 10-Year National Program for Sub-National Democratic Development (NP-SNDD; 2010-2019)
- The implementation of NP was started in 2011 and extended to 2020 and is divided into three phases or implementation plans (IPs)
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- Royal Government of Cambodia (RGC) stated to recognize the value of decentralized local government, its people and institutions, and the crucial role they play in empowering citizens, delivering quality services and reducing poverty

Cambodia SNA

SNA

- Sub-National Administrations (SNAs) are the first point of contact for citizens
- Promote local decision-making
- Resolve local conflicts
- Facilitate citizen participation and engagement
- Stimulate local development
- Provide essential social and municipal services
- Invest in small-scale infrastructure
- That's the theory.....

Cambodia

Development Cooperation (GIZ and RGC)

- Regional Economic Development Program (RED) – started in October 2007 addresses the aforementioned local disparities and poverty issues
- Three fields of intervention:
 - (i) good governance for local economic development (LED),
 - (ii) promoting an enabling local business environment for micro-, small- and medium-sized enterprises (MSME) and
 - (iii) upgrading of selected agricultural value chains (VC)

Regional Economic Development

Regional Economic Development

- Aims to integrate the strengthening of institutional capacities and governance at subnational level including participatory planning and project implementation (e.g. regional management tools) with measures addressing private sector promotion, skills development and market integration of smallholder farms
- The approach is conceptually based a sustainable model based on resource-efficient and socially inclusive economy
- Supports rural population to have better access to market and to increase economic opportunities of marginalized groups through market-based approaches

Regional Economic Development

Challenges:

- SNAs do not believe that they have the power to offer services beyond the obligatory tasks
- Make use of the general mandate/permissive functions
- Cooperation and dialogue between public authorities, private sector and civil society stakeholders exists but is usually *ad hoc* and lacks structure and long-term goal orientation
- High transaction costs due to bureaucratic obstacles and lack of information slow down the development of businesses and business relationships and create an overall unfavorable environment for micro, small- and medium-sized enterprises (MSME)

Regional Economic Development

Good Governance for LED

- Public authorities, administrations and councils at the provincial and district level are institutionally capacitated in steering and implementing measures
- Technical experts and decision makers of the local administrative level are familiarized with approaches to local economic development (bottom-up and evidence-based policymaking)
- Capacitated to fulfil their respective roles and tasks effectively in the sense of good governance
- Participatory dialogue structures with the local population and representatives of the private sector are strengthened
- Matching Fund scheme is a tool for the promotion of inclusive local economic development with SNA's especially district and municipal administration.

Case 1 - Community market establishment By Chong Kal District Administration

Relevance: The project was highly relevant to the needs of local people – and reflected a project idea raised by citizens at a public forum – as it contributed towards improved management of the main market in the district.

Effectiveness: Stakeholder cooperation was strong. The project managed to secure stakeholder contributions, i.e. 70 sellers paid 300 USD each towards the cost of improved market infrastructure.

Impact: More market space, higher sanitation, tighter security and better income opportunities for sellers including those from poor families.

Sustainability: The substantial stakeholder contributions bodes well for the project's sustainability.

Case 2 - Tourism promotion and improvement in Khnar Po commune, Soutr Nikum district

Relevance: To exploit the local potential for the development of tourism in the area through training on food hygiene, environmental waste management and hospitality and how to protect forest areas in order to attract more tourists and raise local incomes.

Effectiveness: Community forestry faced challenges due to illegal logging and encroachment.

Impact: Tangible results were achieved in the form of increased income from eco-tourism development among project beneficiaries (as revealed during interviews conducted by RED III). The numbers of tourists (domestic and foreign) visiting the eco-tourism site and the community forestry area increased steadily during the project implementation period.

Sustainability: There was strong community participation in project activities.

Case 3: O'Runteas Banh Fishery Community

Relevance: Relevance to local citizens who rely on fisheries resources for their livelihoods as its objectives were to improve the protection of those resources through awareness raising on the Fisheries Law, strengthened community management and other fish conservation measures.

Effectiveness: High project expenditure, all activities were implemented and cooperation between the DMA, the Fisheries Cantonment (which provided technical support), the commune authorities (which mobilized local contributions) and members of the community fishery was effective.

Impact: Community management of the fisheries resources in the district has been improved through a review of the roles and responsibilities of the different stakeholders. Law enforcement has been strengthened through awareness raising on the Fishery Law and placing of signboards. In addition, the project provided three radio phone sets and a boat engine to the community fishery for patrolling, which will contribute towards improved law enforcement, i.e. by detecting illegal fishing practices.

Sustainability: Continued efforts to clamp down on illegal fishing are required.

Common Challenges

- Lack experience in service project formulation and implementation
- Re-scheduling activities and procrastinating due to major events such as commune election, relocation of board of governors and public holidays, Khmer New Year celebration, Pchum Ben, took place in implementation timeframe and slowed down the processes
- Market price: The price of the items quoted at the time of the project study increased much higher during the implementation period

Learnings

- Stakeholder cooperation → jointly prepare project activities and design implementation
- Resource mobilization → should not be focused only on local people but also approached to NGOs/INGOs to match with the fund supported by RED
- Clear guidance and process → capacity development measures were provided with technical support for project formulation and implementation
- Continue capacity building measures to fulfil SNA mandate with best results
- Well-functioning of project management committee
- Problem solving → PMC cooperatively discussed and sort out the challenges, problems occurred during the project implementation
- Financial management → cash advance and settlement processes to be used for DMA internal financial management and transparency
- Service project gave direct benefit for local people especially the poor

Learnings

- Concept of Governance has evolved over the years shifted from top down to bottom up
- Current approach of Cambodia is top down depending on the political situation
- Lack of communication between government and rural authorities
- Certain issues do not directly affect sometimes in rural area
- If serious greater political flexibility at the subnational level is made possible with the participation of all relevant population groups, good governance is also conceivable in the supposed one-party state

Implications

- Consistent maintenance of the initiatives and long-term strategic planning
- Sustainability: define different sources of income and create ownership
- With respect to theory: **Regional/Tourism development** of particular areas/products is mostly done through networks
- Strongly support networking capability as this seems to increase power and confidence
- Concept of Governance and Destination Governance arose from advanced economies with long history in tourism and DMO experience -> not so easy to apply in LCD countries
- Work with the system not against it

Literature

- Beritelli, P., Bieger, T., & Laesser, C. (2007). Destination Governance: Using Corporate Governance Theories as a Foundation for Effective Destination Management. *Journal of Travel Research*, 46(1), 96-107
- Costa, C., Costa, R., & Breda, Z. (2006). Do clusters and networks make small places beautiful? The case of Caramulo (Portugal) *Tourism local systems and networking* (pp. 81-96): Routledge.
- Grindle, M. S. (2004). Good enough governance: poverty reduction and reform in developing countries. *Governance*, 17(4), 525-548.
- Joppe, M. (2018). Tourism policy and governance: Quo vadis? *Tourism Management Perspectives*, 25, 201-204.
- Saretzki, A., Wöhler, K., & Dies. (2013b). Governance statt Management oder: Management der Governance. *Governance von Destinationen. Neue Ansätze für die erfolgreiche Steuerung touristischer Zielgebiete*, 3-18.
- Van Assche, K., Beunen, R., & Duineveld, M. (2013). *Evolutionary governance theory: an introduction*: Springer.

Thank you for your attention

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